

D7.2 Ethics Guidelines

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Report Information

Grant Agreement / Proposal ID	101157447
Project Title	Geologically Enhanced Nature-based Solutions for climate change resiliency of critical water InfraStructure
Project Acronym	GENESIS
Project Coordinator	Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas
Project starting date / end date	01/09/2024 – 31/08/2028
Related Work Package	WP7
Lead Organisation	CSIC
Document title	Ethics Guidelines
Submission Date	January 2025
Dissemination level	Public
DOI	https://10.5281/zenodo.14723894

Quality verification

Prepared by	Checked by	Verified by	Approved by
Gerardo Meixueiro	Ajay Jones	Laia D'armengol	Alejandro García

Revision History

Revision	Revision Date	Changes	Authorised	Function
1	14/01/2025	Advanced draft	Gerardo Meixueiro	CSIC Project Manager
2	19/01/2025	Suggestions from reviewers	Daniel Reyes Pavlos Tyrologou Laia D'armengol	ITC Partner EFG Partner LPRC Partner
3	31/01/2025	Final version	Alejandro García	CSIC Project Coordinator

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The GENESIS project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101157447. The sole responsibility for the content of this publication lies with the authors. It does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the Innovation and Networks Executive Agency (INEA) or the European Commission (EC). INEA or the EC are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

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Executive summary

The present Ethics Requirements document is a deliverable of GENESIS Project, funded from the European Union's Horizon Miss 2023 clima-01-02 programme under Grant Agreement No 101157447: Geologically Enhanced Nature-based Solutions for climate change resiliency of critical water InfraStructure.

It provides the Ethical Guidelines and Procedure that all GENESIS consortium members will adhere to. This deliverable consists of two sections after the introduction.

Chapter 2 describes the management of ethical issues within GENESIS. It describes the appointment of an internal Ethical Advisor, the procedure to be followed in case of scientific misconduct, and the scope and objectives of the deliverable.

Chapter 3 describes the principles of good research practice that all researchers of GENESIS will comply to and the ethics management methodology and guidelines that have to be followed.

Chapter 4 explains how all the activities related to data management will be performed in full compliance with the following EU legislation and directives.

And finally, chapter 5 outlines a series of ethical guidelines and procedures that cover the entire research cycle. The annex provides the template of the Data Privacy Information, Voluntary Participation Form, Declaration of Consent and Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA).

This document complements the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement and should be used alongside these two documents. In case of any inconsistencies, the Grant Agreement will take precedence over all other documents, and the Consortium Agreement will take precedence over the Ethics Guidelines.

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1- Introduction

GENESIS will test to their limits and bring to the table innovative NaturE-based Solutions (NbS), including dry gallery and underground dike-impounded dam systems conceived in Macaronesia. Macaronesian NaturE-based Solutions combined with state-of-the art NaturE-based Solutions, such as rainwater harvesting, wetland restoration, and ecosystem-based approaches, will allow advances in a multiple nature-based approach that will create synergistic effects to be investigated.

These NaturE-based Solutions are designed to capture and recover more than 10 hm³ of runoff from stormwater, storing it underground during the initial stages of implementation. Throughout the project, the capacity for underground reservoir storage of fresh water will be expanded to more than 50 hm³ per year across the Macaronesia region, ensuring a sustainable water supply for irrigation. In total, approximately 35,000 residents will directly benefit from the provision of fresh water through the GENESIS project.

However, during these activities certain ethical issues may arise. As a research and innovation project, GENESIS has a responsibility to the people involved in the research and their rights, safety, well-being and interest, the communities that are engaged and involved in the research and the society at large (European Commission, 2018). Therefore, ethics should be safeguarded throughout the whole life circle of the GENESIS project.

To deal with these issues appropriately, ethical guidelines and procedures will be outlined in this document. The purpose of this deliverable is to serve as a practical tool that provides guidance concerning ethical issues for all partners of the GENESIS project. All GENESIS partners are expected to adhere to these guidelines in all GENESIS activities.

The Ethics Guidelines is based on the terms and conditions outlined in the Horizon Europe Grant Agreement no. 101157447 and its Annexes, as well as in the GENESIS Consortium Agreement. In the event of any discrepancies, the Grant Agreement takes precedence over all other documents, and the Consortium Agreement takes precedence over this plan.

It is important to note that this document functions as a guiding tool for the project, offering more extensive details on various aspects of ethics guidelines.

2- Scope of the Deliverable

The present ethics manual document describes the ethical and legal issues that may arise within the GENESIS project, along with the methodology that will be used to collect, store and process the data. The main objectives of the ethics manual are to:

- Establish an ethics management methodology, which takes into account the ethical requirements of all demonstration activities in the pilot sites of the project.
- Outline current European and national legislation in pilot sites, and assure compliance.
- Describe the role of the GENESIS Ethical Advisory Board.
- Provide a template for consent forms.
-

2.1 Detailed overview

GENESIS will apply the ethical standards and guidelines of Horizon Europe¹, regardless of the country in which the pilot site is located. Specific support actions regarding protection of personal data will be provided. This support will be done depending on the specific needs of each pilot site.

The GENESIS project anticipates no ethical issues or risks in its implementation. The Nature-based Solutions (NbS) outlined in the project aim to positively impact the environment, enhance human well-being, and mitigate the adverse effects of climate change.

At this starting point, it needs to be clear for all applicants, according to the Regulation (EU) No 1291/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2013 (article 19)², that:

1. All the research and innovation activities carried out under Horizon shall comply with *Ethical principles* (including the highest standards of research integrity) and the *Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union*³ and the *European Convention on Human Rights and its Supplementary Protocols*⁴. Particular attention shall be paid to the principle of proportionality, the right to privacy, the right to the protection of personal data, the right to the physical and mental integrity of a person, the right to non-discrimination and the need to ensure high levels of human health protection.

2. The following fields of research shall not be financed:

- (a) research activity aiming at human cloning for reproductive purposes;
- (b) research activity intended to modify the genetic heritage of human beings which could make such changes heritable;

¹https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/how-to-complete-your-ethics-self-assessment_en.pdf

²<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2013/1291/oj/eng>

³<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/es/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A12012P%2FTXT>

⁴https://www.echr.coe.int/Documents/Convention_ENG.pdf

(c) research activities intended to create human embryos solely for the purpose of research or for the purpose of stem cell procurement, including by means of somatic cell nuclear transfer.

(d) lead to the destruction of human embryos (for example, for obtaining stem cells).

3. Research on human stem cells, both adult and embryonic, and on animals will not be financed in the GENESIS framework. No funding shall be granted for research activities that are prohibited in all the Member States.

In addition, the beneficiaries must respect the fundamental principle of research integrity as set out in the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity⁵ and means that beneficiaries must ensure that persons carrying out research tasks follow the good research practices including ensuring, where possible, openness, reproducibility and traceability and refrain from the research integrity violations described in the Code.

Within the GENESIS project, a participatory and co-creation methodology is envisaged to engage various regional stakeholders in the design of NbS and the development of regional solutions and a digital ecosystem. The involvement of human participants is planned to be executed under WP2, which will include the following detailed activities:

Main tasks:

- Task 2.1 Assessment of social acceptability of nature-based solutions.
- Task 2.2 Innovative approaches to encourage citizen participation.
- Task 2.3. Bridging science, policy and society: GENESIS citizen science hub.
- Task 2.4. Creating research-based physical and social geoscience experiences for young geoscientists - NbS La Palma Training Bootcamp.

Detailed activities:

- Mapping stakeholders at various scales to incorporate the Quadruple/Quintuple Helix, encompassing academia, policymakers, key community systems across different sectors, civil society, and environmentalists.
- Analysing and reviewing existing regional, national, and EU regulations and policies concerning environmental protection and hazards.
- Employing citizen engagement methodologies, including the organization of specific events and citizen science campaigns (participatory living labs).
- Creating questionnaires tailored to different regions to discern the motivations of participants.
- Compiling and formulating recommendations for regional entities regarding the planning and design of Nature-based Solutions (NbS).
- Establishing competency groups to facilitate discussions on results, best practices, and recommendations across transformation living labs.

This Ethics Report contains detailed information on the procedures that will be implemented for data collection, storage, protection, retention and destruction and confirmation that they comply with national and EU legislation.

⁵ [European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity of ALLEA \(All European Academies\).](#)

It also includes templates of:

- a) the self-assessment ethics issues checklist,
- b) participant information sheet,
- c) GENESIS consent form, that will be implemented.

The Self-assessment Ethics Issues Checklist (ANNEX B) will be completed by all Partners from GENESIS Project. It includes the ethics issues checklist, in order for the applicants to fulfill the ethics self-assessment.

The Voluntary Participant Form (ANNEX C) will be completed by participants of all different regions of GENESIS Project.

The participant information sheet will outline the research intentions and provide details on how the funded Project will be ethical-smoothly implemented.

Finally, GENESIS Consent Form Indicative Example (ANNEX D) must be completed by all Partners performing research activities that involve data collection from external participants, will adapt the form and ask for informed consent to participants. By completing the consent form, the project Partners agree that they need to be in compliance with the ethical guidelines of Horizon, regarding the procedures that will be followed during the lifetime of the funded Project.

2.2 Structure of the Deliverable

The document is structured as follows:

Section 2 presents scope of the deliverable.

Section 3 presents the Ethics Management methodology, which includes several phases.

EU and national legislation and directives related to the countries where the data collection will be performed, are outlined in section 4.

Section 5 presents ethics management, such as the formulation of the Ethical Advisory Board, protection of personal data, as well as other topics.

Section 6 provides a summary of the conclusions and closing remarks.

Finally, useful templates (e.g., Consent Form Indicative Example) are provided in the ANNEXES.

2.3 Relating Tasks and Deliverables

Main inputs that were utilized for preparing this document are the GENESIS Grant Agreement document and online sources for retrieving information about the EU General Data Protection Regulation and legislation of countries where the pilot sites are located.

The methodology and procedures provided in this ethics manual will be utilized as input in the following deliverables:

- D2.1 GENESIS water governance framework of social acceptability.
- D2.2 Guidelines for public engagement and dialogue.
- D2.3 GENESIS citizen science hub
- D2.4 Evaluation report - NbS La Palma Training Bootcamp.

3 GENESIS ethics management methodology

This section presents the GENESIS ethics management methodology. Initially, ethical issues and requirements of the project are identified. The methodology framework provides guidelines that have to be followed, from data collection phase to pilot evaluation and exploitation, in accordance with the ethical requirements.

3.1 Ethical Issues and Requirements

GENESIS consortium members will consider the following actions / guidelines (ethical requirements) when performing an activity that involves data collection from end-users.

1. Provide informed Voluntary Participation Forms for the participation of humans.
2. Provide information about data management process: collection, storage, protection, retention, handling and destruction, according to national and EU legislation.
3. Provide Non-Disclosure Agreements to be signed among consortium members to ensure proper information exchange within GENESIS activities (ANNEX E).
4. Acquire confirmation by the Data Protection Officer and obtain authorization by the corresponding National Data Protection Authority (according to GDPR and national laws).
5. Provide reasonable justification for collecting and processing personal data.
6. Prior to both pre-piloting phase and pilot deployment, all involved end-users must agree and sign informed consents.
7. Prior to final integration and piloting, all foreseen NDAs will have been signed by the involved consortium members.
8. All personal data will be held private and will be pseudo-anonymised as soon as possible during data processing.

3.2 Methodology and Guidelines

The ethics management methodology defines four phases that need to be followed to support the pilots' activities from the ethical and applicable legislation. Figure 1 depicts the main phases of the ethics management methodology, which are:

Planning: During the planning phase, the ethical requirements are defined according to EU and national legislation that applies to each location. Furthermore, preparation of necessary documents, such as the Informed Consents, is taking place.

Ethics Management Principles: Based on the output of the planning phase, the procedures and guidelines that will be followed are defined in the ethics management phase. Privacy and security risks are identified and mitigation measures are established.

Data Management Plan: This phase defines the procedures for ensuring that the data management process complies with EU and national legislation and will be describe in the Deliverable 7.3 Initial Data Management Plan.

Pre-validation and Pilot Activities: During the pre-validation and pilot activities phase, the recruitment of participants is performed in compliance with GDPR and national laws. Informed Consents are signed by the participants beforehand, as well as agreements regarding data access and exchange among project Partners.

Figure 1. Ethics Management Methodology.

The methodology described above has to be followed in order to ensure that:

- All activities of GENESIS project regarding data management comply with EU and national laws and directives.
- The participants are fully aware about the data that will be collected and the reasons for collecting them.
- No sensitive data will be shared to external parties.
- Data collected will not be sold or used for any other purpose that is not relevant to the GENESIS project.
- Only necessary data to accomplish the research will be collected.

4 Legislation

GENESIS project involves data collection at the pilot sites in order to evaluate the technology solutions, as well as data collection at selected buildings for initial technology testing during the pre-validation phase. To this end, human participants will be involved in activities related to data collection and monitoring of several parameters at their premises, as well as participation in surveys and interviews. Since these activities can raise privacy and data protection issues, data collection and processing will be carried out in full compliance with European legislation and directives relevant to the country where they are taking place.

4.1 European Legislation

All activities related to data management will be performed in full compliance with the following European (EU) legislation and directives:

- The Universal Declaration of Human Rights and the Convention 108 for the Protection of Individuals with Regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data.
- General Data Protection Regulation & Directive 2002/58/EC of the European parliament regarding issues with privacy and protection of personal data and the free movement of such data.

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [1] is a privacy and security law which was drafted and passed by the European Union (EU), and imposes obligations onto organizations anywhere, as long as they target or collect data related to people in the EU.

The regulation was put into effect on May 25, 2018. With the GDPR, Europe is signaling its firm stance on data privacy and security at a time when more people are entrusting their personal data with cloud services and breaches are a daily occurrence.

Privacy and Electronic Communications Directive 2002/58/EC on Privacy and Electronic Communications, also known as ePrivacy Directive, is an EU directive on data protection and privacy in the digital age. This directive deals with the regulation of a number of important issues such as confidentiality of information, treatment of traffic data, spam and cookies. The full text of the directive is accessible at [2].

Regarding GDPR, Article 4 presents the list of the definitions that are used for the purposes of the regulation. Indicatively, 'personal data' are defined as:

“any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ('data subject'); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person;”

Furthermore, data 'controller' and 'processor' are defined as follows:

“controller means the natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data; where the purposes and means of such processing are determined by Union or Member State law, the controller or the specific criteria for its nomination may be provided for by Union or Member State law;”

“processor means a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which processes personal data on behalf of the controller;”

A GDPR checklist [3] for data controllers is provided in ANNEX A. The checklist includes basic statements and actions that can help a data controller to limit exposure to regulatory penalties.

In Article 5.1-2 of GDPR, 7 protection and accountability principles related to processing of personal data are outlined. These principles must be considered before and during the data processing phase:

- Lawfulness, fairness and transparency - Processing must be lawful, fair, and transparent to the data subject.
- Purpose limitation - Data must be processed for the legitimate purposes specified explicitly to the data subject when they were collected.
- Data minimization - Only as much data as absolutely necessary for the purposes specified should be collected and processed.
- Accuracy - Personal data must be kept accurate and up to date, where necessary. Every reasonable step must be taken to make sure that inaccurate personal data, having regard to the purposes for which they are processed, are erased or rectified without delay.
- Storage limitation - Personally identifying data may be stored only for as long as necessary for the specified purpose. Personal data may be stored for longer periods insofar as the personal data will be processed solely for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes in accordance with Article 89.
- Integrity and confidentiality - Processing must be done in such a way as to ensure appropriate security, integrity, and confidentiality (e.g., by using encryption).
- Accountability - The data controller is responsible for being able to demonstrate GDPR compliance with all of these principles.

Special attention should be paid during the project to processing of special categories of personal data, as described in Article 9 of GDPR:

“Processing of personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person’s sex life or sexual orientation shall be prohibited.”

These types of personal data are not related to the scope of GENESIS, therefore collection and processing of such data will be avoided.

A **Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA)** is a process aimed to evaluate risks to the rights and freedoms of individuals, in particular the risks’ origin, nature, particularity and severity. Moreover, it analyses measures, safeguards, controls and mechanisms to address these risks, in order to protect personal data.

GDPR foresees the DPIA as a key instrument to enhance data controllers' accountability as it helps them build and demonstrate compliance. The DPIA supports data controllers in establishing the rules for collecting personal data with regard to proportionality of collection to the purpose of processing and legal basis. DPIA facilitates data protection by design and complements risk management processes. According to the GDPR, DPIAs should be carried out in order to evaluate the origin, nature, particularity and severity of a risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons. A DPIA is mandatory in case:

- Special categories of data (e.g., sensitive data) are processed on a large scale.
- A new technology will be deployed and tested.
- A profiling operation is susceptible to affect people in a significant manner.

The GENESIS consortium will monitor ongoing work of regulatory bodies and relevant data protection recommendations and its Ethical Advisory Board (EAB) in the field of the regulatory environment for privacy, data protection and information security, to ensure adaptation and conformance. Moreover, GENESIS aims to actively contribute to ongoing work of regulation bodies and EAB.

In GENESIS, data collection and processing for the adoption of NbS that build systemic climate resilience in the communities in the area of influence of each demonstration demonstrator site within NbS Mainstreaming and Social Engagement (WP2). GENESIS consortium members are committed to treat the data anonymously.

In relation to data handling activities, the pilot site partners will act as *controllers*, while the partners that will process and analyse the data will have the role of *processors*.

The controllers will follow certain steps to ensure compliance with the GDPR, such as (a) the engagement of Data Protection Officer (DPO) for each pilot site, and (b) ensuring that only the anonymous data will be shared with the processors. The DPO will monitor compliance with GDPR and internal policies, and will provide advice on the necessity and implementation of DPIAs.

In case a company or organisation is not required to employ a DPO, the corresponding Ethical Advisory Board member will be employed instead. Moreover, the controller will be responsible for compliance with the Article 30 of GDPR – Records of processing activities [4], where the following statements are included among others.

“Each controller and, where applicable, the controller’s representative, shall maintain a record of processing activities under its responsibility. Each processor and, where applicable, the processor’s representative shall maintain a record of all categories of processing activities carried out on behalf of a controller. The controller or the processor and, where applicable, the controller’s or the processor’s representative, shall make the record available to the supervisory authority on request.”

5 GENESIS Ethical management

GENESIS consortium is aware that the protection of personal data is of utmost importance and it will ensure that all necessary measures will be taken to protect the privacy of the data subjects involved. This section presents the measures that will be taken by the consortium complying with the EU and national legislation outlined in the previous section.

5.1 Ethical Advisory Board

The Ethical Advisory Board (EAB) will provide ongoing support concerning ethical and legal issues to the consortium, including support on privacy issues related to data collection in pilot sites. Moreover, it will provide guidelines and recommendations to consortium partners involved in the development of GENESIS tools, as well as to end users in the pilot sites. To ensure ethical compliance throughout the entire GENESIS project, GENESIS has appointed Ajay Jones (VPCGT) as the Ethical Advisor (EA) is responsible for:

- Ensuring the proper management of all ethics procedures.
- Reviewing all created GENESIS materials and outputs for ethical compliance.

The EAB will monitor and oversee the pilots, validation and evaluation of GENESIS results in terms of ethics, security and privacy requirements. In particular, EAB will warrant that all technical activities, trials, data management and data processing will be carried out in an ethical way that respects privacy and regulatory constraints. The EAB is composed of persons from 4 different partners of the GENESIS project.

The synthesis of the GENESIS EAB is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Ethical Advisory Board.

Partner	Person name	Email
ITC	Daniel Reyes	dreyes@itccanarias.org
LPRC	Laia D'armengol	laia.dearmengol@lapalmacentre.eu
VPCGT	Ajay Jones	ajay@geotenerife.com

5.2 Ethical considerations in post-project exploitation

The GENESIS project results will be immediately applied to design NbS for safeguarding critical water infrastructures, such as groundwater. The La Palma Living Lab and Training Boot Camp will support replication and long-term investment. Sharing datasets in EU data spaces will drive innovation at all levels, from IT/algorithms to geophysical and social sciences research, benefiting communities focused on climate resilience.

Partners plan to individually exploit GENESIS results. Research institutes (e.g., CSIC, IST-ID, ITC, LNEG, UCV, ULL, UMA, ULR) will gain new knowledge to advance their expertise and apply innovation in various sectors.

International, national, and local associations will contribute to open science missions and enhance governance and citizen participation (e.g., ALDA). The main beneficiaries of GENESIS will be local governments, authorities, communities, and both for-profit and non-profit companies.

5.3 Protection of Personal Data

Certain procedures have been defined for management of personal data, in order to protect individuals and their rights in compliance with EU legislation. All used assessment tools, data collection and analysis protocols within the GENESIS project will be verified in advance by the EAB.

The consortium will follow the advice of expert committees in the field, such as the European Group on Ethics (EGE) in science and new technologies [5]. The EGE is an independent advisory body of the President of the European Commission, which provides high quality, independent advice on ethical aspects of science and new technologies in relation to EU legislation or policies. In addition, all national legal and ethical requirements of the Member States where the research is performed will be fulfilled. Any data collection and storage involving humans will be strictly held confidential at any time of the research.

The following procedures will take place:

- All participants will be informed and given the opportunity to provide their consent to any monitoring and data acquisition process. All subjects will be strictly volunteers and all test volunteers receive detailed oral information;
- No personal data will be centrally stored. In addition, personal data will be pseudo-anonymised, in a way that will not affect the final project outcome.

In addition, participants will receive in their own language in conformity with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR):

- A commonly understandable written description of the project and its goals;
- The planned project progress and the related testing and evaluation procedures;
- Advice on unrestricted disclaimer rights on their agreement.

The EAB will scrutinise the research to guarantee that no undue risk for the user, neither technical, nor related to the breach of privacy is possible. Thus, the consortium will implement the research project in full respect of the legal and ethical national requirements and code of practice. Whenever authorisations have to be obtained from national bodies, those authorisations shall be considered as documents relevant to the project. Copies of all relevant authorisations shall be submitted to the Commission prior to commencement of the relevant part of the research project.

5.4 Procedures and Criteria for Identification/Recruitment of Research Participants

Volunteer end users will participate in activities related to the use case scenarios that will be evaluated within WP2. These participants will be contacted by the project partners to ensure that they are both relevant and appropriate for the project. Vulnerable participants or minors will not be recruited in experimental activities.

In accordance with Article 43 of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the recruitment method and informed consent procedures will be particularly stringent to ensure no coercion (not even soft or indirect) is exerted. The specific criteria for the selection of the volunteer participants will be determined for each experimental study (T8.2).

According to GDPR, personal data constitutes any information related to a natural person or 'Data Subject', that can be used to directly or indirectly identify the person. It can be anything from a name, a photo, an email address, bank details, posts on social networking websites, medical information, or a computer IP address.

As a result, specific measures will be undertaken to protect the volunteer participants from a breach of privacy/confidentiality and potential discrimination.

Regarding confidentiality, it should be mentioned that the personal data of all research participants that will be recruited through informed consents will be never revealed in any document.

All personal data (requested in the informed consent) will be completely and irreversibly pseudo-anonymised and will be erased after the completion of the project.

Upon applying the pseudo-anonymization process, the personal data will be transformed to encrypted personal data.

As a result, they will not contain any of the following:

- Name, address, posts on social networking websites, phone/fax. number(s), e-mail address, full postcode;
- Any identifying reference numbers;
- Photograph or names of relatives;
- Medical information;
- Bank details;
- Computer IP addresses.

5.5 Informed Consent Procedures and Guidelines for the Participation of Humans

It is expected that several project activities will imply processing of personal data and therefore, fall within the scope of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Therefore, informed consent procedures must be implemented for the participation of humans. GENESIS will collect and store personal data only if it is absolutely necessary for achieving the project aim and will whenever possible process encrypted personal data only.

Research on personal data that has been collected on a legal basis will be carried out on condition that the consent of data subjects exists.

The research participants' consent will be obtained through a two-stage procedure:

- Initially the respective Partner will orally describe the pilot in which people will be involved and will also carefully describe the level of privacy infringement that the pilot involves. In case the person wants to exercise his/her right not to know, he/she will be excluded by the pilot.
- Secondly, after a few days, subjects will be required to read and sign an informed consent form that will explain in plain English and in local language what the experiment leader has already orally explained. Informed consent forms in English and in local language will be sent to the Ethical Advisory Board (EAB) and included in the experimental protocol. A consent form template and an example are provided in ANNEX D.

The consortium will take the appropriate actions to exclude that:

1. Data can be collected without the explicit informed consent of people under observation; no person unable to express a free and informed consent for age-related reasons, ongoing medical and/or psychological conditions, mental incapacity, will be participate in Use case activities;
2. Data collected may be sold or used for any different purposes from the GENESIS project;
3. Any data, which is not strictly necessary to accomplish the current study, will be collected; data minimisation policy will be adopted at any level of the project and will be supervised by the ethical/privacy component of the project;
4. Any shadow (ancillary) personal data obtained in the course of the observation will be immediately cancelled. However, we plan to minimize as far as possible this kind of ancillary data.

Special attention will be also paid to comply with Council of Europe's Recommendation R(87)15 on the processing of personal data for police purposes, Art.2: "*The collection of data on individuals solely on the basis that they have a particular racial origin, particular religious convictions, sexual behavior or political opinions or belong to particular movements or organisations which are not proscribed by law should be prohibited. The collection of data concerning these factors may only be carried out if absolutely necessary for the purposes of a particular inquiry*". Some sessions between technical and ethical components of the project will be devoted to this.

6 Conclusions

This document presented the ethical requirements and ethics related guidelines to be followed within the duration of GENESIS project, and it will serve as an ethics manual. Various types of data will be collected from the pilot sites located on different islands in different countries, involving human participants.

Therefore, the necessary measures that will be taken to protect the privacy of the data subjects involved were described. The data management procedures will be performed in accordance with EU and national legislation of the countries involved in the data collection locations. An outline of relevant legislation and regulations was presented in this document.

Moreover, an ethics management methodology was defined and presented along with important ethics principles that will be considered.

The GENESIS Ethical Advisory Board (EAB) has been formed for ensuring that all project measures are performed in compliance with both the EU and national legislation, and will monitor the application of the GENESIS ethical framework.

Finally, procedures related to the protection of private data, identification/recruitment of research participants, and the delivery of the Informed Consent were presented.

7 References

- [1]. <https://gdpr.eu/>
- [2]. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=CELEX:32002L0058:en:HTML>
- [3]. <https://gdpr.eu/checklist/>
- [4]. <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-30-gdpr/>
- [5]. European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies - https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/strategy/support-policy-making/scientific-support-eu-policies/ege_en

ANNEX A: GDPR Checklist

1. Lawful basis and transparency	Yes	No	Page
Contact an information audit to determine what information you process and who has access to it.			
Have a legal justification for your data processing activities.			
Provide clear information about your data processing and legal justification in your privacy policy.			
2. Data security			
Take data protection into account at all times, from the moment you begin developing a product to each time you process data.			
Encrypt, pseudonymize, or anonymize personal data wherever possible.			
Create an internal security policy for your team members, and build awareness about data protection.			
Know when to conduct a data protection impact assessment, and have a process in place to carry it out.			
Have a process in place to notify the authorities and your data subjects in the event of a data breach.			
3. Accountability and governance			
Designate someone responsible for ensuring GDPR compliance across your organization.			
Sign a data processing agreement between your organization and any third parties that process personal data on your behalf.			
If your organization is outside the EU, appoint a representative within one of the EU member states.			
Appoint a Data Protection Officer (if necessary).			
4. Privacy rights			
It is easy for your customers to request and receive all the information you have about them.			
It is easy for your customers to request to have their personal data deleted.			
It is easy for your customers to request to have their personal data deleted.			
It is easy for your customers to ask you to stop processing their data.			
It is easy for your customers to receive copy of their personal data in a format that can be easily transferred to another company.			
It is easy for your customers to object to you processing their data.			
If you make decisions about people based on automated processes, you have a procedure to protect their rights.			

ANNEX B: Self-assessment ethics issues checklist

	Yes	No	Page
1. Human embryos / fetuses			
Does your research involve Human Embryonic Stem Cells (hESCs)?			
Does your research involve the use of human embryos?			
Does your research involve the use of human fetal tissues / cells?			
2. Humans			
Does your research involve human participants?			
Does your research involve physical interventions on the study participants?			
3. Human cells / tissues			
Does your research involve human cells or tissues (other than from Human Embryos/Fetuses, i.e. section 1)?			
4. Personal data			
Does your research involve personal data collection and/or processing?			
5. Animals			
Does your research involve animals?			
6. Third countries			
In case non-EU countries are involved, do the research related activities undertaken in these countries raise potential ethics issues?			
Do you plan to use local resources (e.g. animal and/or human tissue samples, genetic material, live animals, human remains, materials of historical value, endangered fauna or flora samples, etc.)?			
Do you plan to import any material - including personal data - from non-EU countries into the EU?			
Do you plan to export any material - including personal data - from the EU to non-EU countries?			
Could the situation in the country put the individuals taking part in the research at risk?			
7. Environment & health and safety			
Does your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to the environment, to animals or plants?			
Does your research deal with endangered fauna and/or flora and/or protected areas?			
Does your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to humans, including research staff?			
8. Dual use			
Does your research involve dual-use items in the sense of Regulation 428/2009, or other items for which an authorization is required?			
9. Exclusive focus on civil applications			
Could your research raise concerns regarding the exclusive focus on civil applications?			
10. Misuse			
Does your research have the potential for misuse of research results?			
11. Other ethics issues			
Are there any other ethics issues that should be taken into consideration? Please specify.			

ANNEX C: Voluntary Participation Form

1. Participant's Information		
Full name		
Reference code		
2. Study Information		
Country		
Infrastructure type		
Infrastructure address		
Representative of the pilot		
3. Participant's Questionnaire		
I have read the GENESIS project information sheet and I have been informed about the purpose, expected duration and procedures of the study.	Yes	No
I was orally informed about the purpose, expected duration and procedures of the study by the responsible person.	Yes	No
I was informed of my right to refuse to participate or to leave the study.	Yes	No
I was notified of the contact person, in the case I have questions and queries about the study or about my personal data being collected.	Yes	No
I was given a copy of my filled in consent form.	Yes	No
I had enough time to decide on my participation in the study.	Yes	No
I understand that I can leave the study at any time, without having to justify it and to require deleting my personal data.	Yes	No
I have been informed of the recording equipment that will be installed in my environment for the purposes of data collection.	Yes	No
I was informed about the storage procedures of the study data.	Yes	No
I was informed about the personal data that will be collected, the processors and the procedures that will take place, as well as my rights according to the General Data Protection Regulation. Publication of study results does not disclose personal data. Always according to the principles of confidentiality, I allow researchers involved in the study and signing respective NDAs can utilize the information for the purpose of the study and only for this.	Yes	No
I agree to the use of the collected data also after the termination of the GENESIS project.	Yes	No
I agree to participate in the study.	Yes	No

Date: _____

Signature: _____

ANNEX D: Consent Form Indicative Example

Project Purpose

- A commonly understandable written description of the project and its goals even for people that are not familiar to the project scope (2-3 paragraphs)

Project Progress Schedule

- The progress schedule of the project and the related testing and evaluation procedures (1-2 paragraphs)

Disclaimer Rights

- Advice on unrestricted disclaimer rights on their agreement.

Voluntary Participation Form

1. General Information

- Participant basic information
- ID (reference code) of the participant, which will be used throughout the pilot trial execution

2. Study Information

- Details about the pilot cases

3. Participant's Questionnaire

- has been fully informed on the purpose, duration, procedures of the study;
- has been informed on the rights to deny participating or to quit from the study and about the corresponding consequences.
- has been informed on the contact person in case that I have questions and queries about the study.
- had adequate time to make my decision concerning my participation in the study.
- comprehend that he/she can quit from the study at any time without having to justify his/her decision.
- has been informed about potential effects, difficulties and dangers.
- has been informed about the sensors equipment that will be used to collect data.
- has been informed about the security of the study data and results.
- has been ensured about the confidentiality of his/her personal information. Publications of the study results do not allow the personal data recognition, due to the principle of anonymity. Always under the confidentiality principles.

4. Signed Consent to Participate

- A signed consent of the participant allowing the study responsible to examine and inspect the data collected during the study.

ANNEX E: Non-Disclosure Agreement

Non-Disclosure Agreement

CONFIDENTIAL DISCLOSURE AGREEMENT

THIS AGREEMENT dated DD/MM/YYYY, by and between [Name of the Data Owner] (“Discloser”) and [Name of the GENESIS Partner] (“Recipient”).

WHEREAS, [Discloser] and [Recipient], for the purpose of establishing a cooperative relationship and pursuant to the research related to GENESIS project, anticipate that [Discloser] may disclose or deliver to [Recipient] building data and information, energy consumption information, building occupancy information, drawings, data, sketches, specifications, and other materials, both written and oral, of a secret, confidential or proprietary nature, including without limitation any and all information relating to marketing, finance, forecasts, research, prepared or filed by or behalf of by [Discloser], in any jurisdiction, and any amendments or supplements thereto (collectively, “Proprietary Information”); and

WHEREAS, [Discloser] desires to assure that the confidentiality of any Proprietary Information is maintained;

NOW, THEREFORE, in consideration of the foregoing premises, and the mutual covenants contained herein, [Discloser] and [Recipient] hereby agree as follows:

1. Under this Agreement the [Recipient] undertakes: (i) to hold in trust and confidence and not disclose, without the express prior written consent of the [Discloser], to any third party (including a Recipient’s Affiliates) or others or use for [Recipient]’s own benefit or for the benefit of any third party or others, any Proprietary Information, in any form, which is disclosed to [Recipient] by [Discloser] at any time and (ii) to carry out all necessary and appropriate measures to ensure that the Proprietary Information is protected against any access by third parties or others. [Recipient] shall disclose Proprietary Information received under this Agreement to person within its organization only if such persons (i) have a need to know and (ii) are bound in writing to protect the confidentiality of such Proprietary Information under the same terms as this Agreement. This paragraph 1 shall survive and continue after any expiration or termination of this Agreement and shall bind [Recipient], its employees, agents, representatives, successors, heirs and assigns. In compliance with the European Union’s General Data Protection Regulation, the [Recipient] agrees to adhere to the confidentiality expectations as outlined in the EU General Data Protection Regulations (GDPR) and require the same of any subcontractors that perform services in conjunction with this Agreement.

In the event that the [Recipient] is required by mandatory law or regulation or by order of a court, government department or agency or recognized stock exchange to disclose any Proprietary Information, the [Recipient] shall provide the [Discloser] with prompt notice of such requirement – to the extent that such notice is permitted by law or regulation – so that the [Discloser] may seek a protective order or other appropriate remedy or waive compliance with the provisions of this Agreement. Whether or not such protective order or other remedy is obtained, or whether the [Discloser] waives compliance with the provisions of this Agreement, a [Recipient] shall disclose only that portion of the Proprietary Information, which is legally required to be disclosed based on the advice of the [Recipient].

2. The undertakings and obligations of [Recipient] under this Agreement shall not apply to any Proprietary Information which: (a) is disclosed in a printed publication available to the

public, or is otherwise in the public domain through no action or fault of [Recipient]; (b) is generally disclosed to third parties by [Discloser] without restriction on such third parties, or is approved for release by written authorization of [Discloser]; or (c) is shown to [Discloser] by [Recipient], within ten (10) days from disclosure, by underlying documentation to have been known by [Recipient] before receipt from [Discloser] and/or to have been developed by [Recipient] completely independent of any disclosure by [Discloser].

3. Title to all property received by [Recipient] from [Discloser], including all Proprietary Information, shall remain at all times the sole property of [Discloser], and this Agreement shall not be construed to grant to [Recipient] any patents, licenses or similar rights to such property and Proprietary Information disclosed to [Recipient] hereunder.

4. [Recipient] shall, upon request of [Discloser], return to [Discloser] all documents, drawings and other materials, including all Proprietary Information and all manifestation thereof, delivered to [Recipient], and all copies and reproductions thereof. Unless required otherwise by mandatory law, the [Recipient] shall destroy all copies of any Proprietary Information. Upon the [Discloser's] request the [Recipient] shall confirm compliance by the [Recipient] with the obligations under this paragraph 4 in writing.

5. The Proprietary Information is provided without any representation or warranty, express or implied, as to its accuracy or completeness. Each Party hereby agrees that the [Recipient] will assume full responsibility for all conclusions that the [Recipient] derives from the Proprietary Information. The [Discloser] shall have no liability with respect to the Proprietary Information, errors therein or omissions there from in any manner and on any legal ground.

6. The parties further agree to the following terms and conditions:

a. The [Recipient] agrees to be fully responsible and liable to the [Discloser] for any actions or failures to act which result in a breach of this Agreement. Any breach by [Recipient] of any of [Recipient]'s obligations under this Agreement will result in irreparable injury to [Discloser] for which damages and other legal remedies will be inadequate. In seeking enforcement of any of these obligations, [Discloser] will be entitled (in addition to other remedies) to preliminary and permanent injunctive and other equitable relief to prevent, discontinue and/or restrain the breach of this Agreement.

b. If any provision of this Agreement is invalid or unenforceable, then such provision shall be construed and limited to the extent necessary, or severed, if necessary, in order to eliminate such invalidity or unenforceability, and the other provisions of this Agreement shall not be affected thereby.

c. In any dispute over whether information or matter is Proprietary Information hereunder, it shall be the burden of [Recipient] to show both that such contested information or matter is not Proprietary Information within the meaning of this Agreement, and that it does not constitute a trade secret.

d. No delay or omission by either party in exercising any rights under this Agreement will operate as a waiver of that or any other right. A waiver or consent given by either party on any one occasion is effective only in that instance and will not be construed as a bar to or waiver of any right on any other occasion.

e. This Agreement shall be binding upon and will inure to the benefit of the parties hereto and their respective successors and assigns.

f. This Agreement is governed by and will be construed in accordance with the law of {COUNTRY}, and the courts of {TOWN}, {COUNTRY} shall be the exclusive forum. (TOWN and COUNTRY is the town and the country of the Discloser respectively).

g. This Agreement is in addition to any prior written agreement between [Discloser] and [Recipient] relating to the subject matter of this agreement; in the event of any disparity or conflict between the provision of such agreements, the provision which is more protective of Proprietary Information shall prevail.

This Agreement may not be modified, in whole or in part, except by an agreement in writing signed by [Discloser] and [Recipient].

IN WITNESS WHEREOF, the parties have executed this Agreement as of the date first above written.

[Discloser]

[RECIPIENT]

By: _____

By: _____

Signature

Signature

Printed Name

Printed Name
